
CRIMINAL INTELLIGENCE MODEL AND CONCEPTS: ANTHROPOLOGICAL ELEMENTS, SOCIOLOGICAL DIMENSIONS

İbrahim Yavuz ^{1 A}; M. Kubilay Akman ^{2 A}

¹ Candidate for master's degree in sociology, e-mail: ibrahimyavuz095@gmail.com

² Prof. Dr., An academic at Uşak University, e-mail: mkakman@uic.es

^A Graduate Education Institute of Uşak University, Uşak, Turkey

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Abstract

Crime has a serious impact in all societies. Government and authorities are trying to find solutions to this big and serious problem. Criminal incidents are topics of researches in security, criminology, sociology and social anthropology. Criminal Intelligence (CRIMINT) is a sub-discipline of intelligence and specialized on analyzing crime in its social, cultural and international contexts. In this article criminal intelligence is discussed in an interdisciplinary way with references to other related scientific fields. Main concepts of CRIMINT are analyzed, Intelligence-led policing (ILP) is focused and also anthropological aspects of crime are explained in order to open new horizons in intelligence studies. Human rights, as a very important value, also have been among the crucial lines of our scientific study here.

Key words: criminal intelligence, intelligence studies, security studies, social anthropology, sociology of crime.

Introduction

Crime is a social phenomenon which analyzed in several disciplines: sociology, social anthropology, criminology, intelligence studies and security studies. Can we stop it, or at least foresee its possible directions and dimensions in accordance with social sciences? There are some patterns analyzed through these disciplines and there are some, let us say, "bad surprises" going beyond any possible prescience and predictions. In this article we will focus on analytical methods and techniques of criminal intelligence (CRIMINT) and their some possible connections with sociological and anthropological points. We neither claim nor argue that all lines of CRIMINT is included here. The text should be considered as a multilayered path touching to different fields and providing discussion topics to both scholars of crime and international officers of respective agencies. CRIMINT is inevitably a practical and pragmatic activity which has nothing to do with philosophical abstractions and transcendental sophistication and skids. This pre-acceptance would be a good measure to see what is functional and what is destined to be outdated by the time.

Result and Discussion

1. Anthropological and criminological aspects

Crime can be defined and described in different ways. What is common in all its variations is that they challenge and threaten the social order. The most common definition of crime is any violation of a set rule, regulation, or law by an individual for which the government or law enforcement agency may eventually prescribe a penalty. Another common definition of crime is any abnormal activity that goes against accepted standards, particularly cultural norms that dictate how people

should behave in general (Miller, 2009: 61). This kind of abnormalities are considered to be “corrected” by societies.

New Criminology criticized existing theories of crime and they argued that “most existing theories of crimes had not looked at a wide enough range of questions”, frequently neglected the material conflicts which are usually the root of criminal actions, often were very deterministic with their assumptions and did not give enough role to creative human actors willing to commit crime and had inadequate epistemologies. They contended that limitations might be found in both the early theories (classicism and positivism) and the so-called radical or skeptical theories (labeling, new deviance, etc.) of the 1970s. These were largely ineffective, and the field as a whole was “exhausted, except as a form of moral gesture”. Some academics in the school of New Criminology believed that the issues facing the working class and impoverished were not the real threats in crime. Instead, the crimes of the powerful were the ones that needed to be highlighted; the wrong crimes and criminals were the ones receiving attention (Carrabine, 2009: 100-101). Were they right? Maybe not; it sounds quite as a politically and ideologically engaged view of the problem. The statistics of crime in the streets would not be really supportive to their arguments.

The groundwork for an anthropological explanation of crime and delinquency was laid by the pioneering theories of sociocultural anthropology in the 19th and 20th century. In their ethnographic research on vanishing peoples, anthropologists have examined unwritten laws, legal infractions, deviations from standards, and class and power disparities in the contemporary globalization era as well as throughout the colonial and industrial centuries. Even while early anthropologists studied small, seemingly simple societies, they now study cultures that are so complex that, ironically, only small segments of larger social groups need to be studied. However, modern anthropologists continue to expand on Boas's original concepts of cultural particularism and holism in order to create a unified field theory that unites the very tiny with the very vast. This is done by addressing both the small local group and its global setting at the same time (Jeroslow, 2011: 266, 268). Even sometimes a made-up word, “glocal” is used for referring the interconnections between the local(ities) and the global.

The historical settings in which the anthropological theories of crime and delinquency were formed as well as the evolving complexity of civilizations across time are reflected in them. The fundamental ideas and ethnographic techniques of earlier anthropological studies of crime are still adhered to by modern scholars studying this topic. For example, anthropological research conducted in the modern era has examined the cultures of adolescent gangs and the mafia, with particular emphasis on the ways in which these groups relate to the broader society in which they operate (Jeroslow, 2011: 255-256, 259). Anthropologists' interest in the worldwide aspect of crime has increased significantly during the 1990s and is still growing now. Post-modern anthropologists are more interested in the connections between crime and the structures of national and international communities than they are in the relationship between laws and crime. Anthropologists study how marginalized populations in post-industrialized countries or those living in developing nations manage to thrive in a globalized economy. They are also looking into criminal activity in nation-state level and corporate criminality. Their research represents a strong political and economic understanding of power dynamics that modern anthropologists integrate with analyses of social structures, symbolic meanings, and psychological constructs surrounding criminal behavior (Jeroslow, 2011: 263). Anthropology, just like sociology, is evolving. This evolution affects its look towards crime and criminal activities.

We have good reasons to say that social stratification and belonging to a particular social class or socio-economic status do not bring people to the same position automatically. We need to “keep in mind that although wealth, power, and prestige are often interrelated, they can also

operate independently". Let us "consider that it is possible to possess both power and wealth while having little prestige, as is the case with leaders of organized crime. Some people, such as classical pianists, may be highly esteemed for their musical virtuosity yet have modest wealth and little power or influence over people" (Ferraro and Andreatta, 2009: 287). This kind of examples show that things can be more complicated than they appear.

According to anthropologist Donald E. Brown's landmark book *Human Universals* (1991), many anthropologists have missed fundamental commonalities in human behavior and culture in their attempts to characterize cultural difference. Because of this, there exist misconceptions and preconceptions regarding members of different societies, who are seen as "exotic", "inscrutable", and "alien". He outlines numerous universal human traits. Brown conjures up a group of individuals in one inventive chapter that he calls the "Universal People", who possess every quality shared by members of every community on the planet (Scupin and DeCorse, 2015: 240). In addition to a complex grammar language that allows them to think abstractly and communicate, the Universal People also have kinship terms and categories that help them distinguish between relatives and age groups, gender terms for men and women, facial expressions that convey basic emotions, and a concept of the self as subject and object. They have tools, shelter, and fire, patterns for childbirth and training, families and political groups, conflict, etiquette, morality, religious beliefs, and worldviews, dance, music, art, and other aesthetic standards too (Scupin and DeCorse, 2015: 240-241). According to Brown's portrayal of the Universal People, a number of issues that jeopardize the social and physical life of all societies are the cause of these and numerous other facets of human conduct. A society needs systems in place to take care of its young, adjust to its physical surroundings, manufacture and supply commodities and services, uphold law and order, and explain its social and natural surroundings. Furthermore, a lot of universal behaviors stem from basic biological traits that all people share (Scupin and DeCorse, 2015: 240-241). The tension an flow between universality and locality have shaped anthropological discussions in many contexts. There are many universal things for sure, however some very important issues are totally local.

In anthropological understanding of crime different schools have different tendencies. With their vastly divergent perspectives on social inequality, functionalists and conflict theorists have been at odds for a long time. According to functionalists, stratification systems are real and essential since they help the societies in which they are embedded. Conflict theorists, on the other hand, contend that stratification systems exist because they support the affluent and powerful, who occupy the top positions, in maintaining their privileged status. The functionalist viewpoint highlights the advantages of social stratification for society as a whole. Conflict theorists call our attention to undesirable features of society, such as the inherent injustice of stratification systems and how it can spark uprisings and high rates of crime (Ferraro and Andreatta, 2009: 308). Structural or conflict-related determinants, regardless what are affecting, in all societies there is crime.

Social norm violations frequently lead to arguments among members of the community. Crimes are what we refer to when these disagreements turn into violent fights (like killing, assault, or theft). Societies must create explicit processes to discuss and, ideally, solve violent conflicts among their members since such conflicts are a possibility. While crime is a part of every community in the world, the prevalence of crime differs greatly throughout societies. Large, diverse, stratified cultures seem to have higher crime rates than smaller, more homogeneous societies (Ferraro and Andreatta, 2009: 333). For instance, the rate of crime in the cities of the USA is roughly ten times higher than that in rural areas. These results are backed by a number of reasonable causes. First, persons in small-scale societies have little to no anonymity which makes it harder to get away with a crime. Second, people in small-scale communities are more likely to be concerned with unfavorable public opinion since they know most of the other people in the community. Third, there are several groups with various interests that occasionally conflict due to the varied nature of

populations in large-scale, complex societies. Lastly, because large-scale societies are nearly always divided into classes or castes, the lower classes may believe that they are unable to advance in society and, as a result, may feel more inclined to desire to violate the rights of the more privileged groups (Ferraro and Andreatta, 2009: 333-334). This would remind us of course the well-known separation between community and society in F. Tönnies's sociology.

2. Criminal Intelligence (CRIMINT) work and tasks

Although we can find some possibilities of anthropological theory which can be provided to intelligence studies it is not really a smooth and plain process. David W. Kriebel said that "it is difficult to find examples in the literature of the application of anthropological theory to intelligence work" (Kriebel, 2015: 79). When the topics of intelligence and security are brought up, it is usually to criticize or at the very least cast doubt on anthropologists' involvement in these fields, or to apply anthropological knowledge to the ways that security or law enforcement agencies operate. Although there are many anthropologists' writings that might be of interest to intelligence analysts, most of them are either statistical associations or descriptive ethnographies that have little to do with theory, or they heavily borrow from other fields like political science, sociology, or psychology. (Kriebel, 2015: 79).

According to Kriebel the future of anthropology in intelligence work is uncertain, not least because of prevailing attitudes within academic anthropology (Kriebel, 2015: 87). He hopes that some anthropological theories and techniques may contribute positively to intelligence work although some other fields, such as social psychology and statistics would be functional too (Kriebel, 2015: 87). The nature of intelligence is driving it to cooperate with other fields of social studies.

The process of giving information a meaning through interpretation can be referred to as intelligence. It has also been used to characterize an organization or division that collects or handles such information, as well as the outcome of such an endeavor or division. The easiest way to define intelligence would be as information that has been processed. When it comes to information used by law enforcement agencies to decide on and support criminal investigations, "intelligence" can be defined as that which is obtained, used, and safeguarded through their operations (UNODC, 2010: 9). Raw, unexamined observations and measurements make up data. Examples include characteristics of criminal activity that are easily measured, like crime statistics and reports, offender databases, and police duties. Information is data that has been given context and meaning, increasing its relevance and usefulness. Information that has been interpreted and comprehended is called knowledge. Knowledge is created when someone adds their wisdom to information. Data, information, and knowledge that have been assessed, examined, and presented in a way that facilitates decision-making for practical objectives is intelligence (OSCE, 2017: 16). Therefore, intelligence is bringing a higher, more comprehensive and powerful level of view.

The process of developing an intelligence knowledge product for use in law enforcement, crime prevention, and reduction is known as criminal intelligence. An intelligence knowledge product in this sense is a product that has the ability to affect a decision-maker's perspective. It is the outcome of a criminal intelligence analysis and may be given verbally in a briefing as a written bulletin, presentation, or some combination of these. An intelligence knowledge product can be even a brief telephone conversation if the intelligence is given timely and has a positive effect on the decision-making process of the recipient of the intelligence (Carter, 2009: 272). Relevance and functionality are important in this context.

Image 1. Criminal Intelligence Cycle (OSCE, 2017: 31)

Information gathered, examined, and/or shared with the intention of foreseeing, averting, or keeping an eye on specific criminal action is called intelligence. In this context, “intelligence” refers to Criminal Intelligence (CRIMINT), which is the goal of information collection, analysis, and distribution in relation to the identification of individuals who are logically suspected of being involved in or about to engage in illegal behavior. In order to acquire information for a prosecution, CRIMINT concentrates on the actions and behaviors of particularly notable offenders or organized groups of likely offenders. Typically, such information is supplied only when necessary and is not widely disseminated (IACP, 2021: 11). Effective law enforcement operations depend heavily on criminal intelligence, and one of the most important aspects of successful intelligence operations within a law enforcement organization is developing a criminal intelligence policy. The policy should specify the purpose, objectives, and standards of the intelligence function as well as the appropriate protocols and constraints for gathering, assessing, auditing, purging, and sharing intelligence. It should also specify who is responsible for carrying out these tasks. This policy should take into account tactics for information exchange, regulatory requirements, and staffing and organization. It is crucial that agency employees comprehend the department’s precise policy so they can follow the right procedures when carrying out criminal intelligence tasks. Guidance to officers and other relevant staff is advantageous to the department’s overall purpose and the productivity of its people, as there are numerous areas that may fall under the purview of criminal intelligence (IACP, 2021: 14). For this purpose institutional education and training are necessary. Employees should be educated continuously.

Image 2. Integration of Intelligence (UNODC, 2011: 35)

The following are among the specific duties assigned to criminal intelligence units:

1. Start investigations and carry out information searches to gather criminal intelligence data on particular crimes that the CEO has identified.
2. Create and manage a system for gathering, analyzing, assessing, storing, compiling, retrieving, and sharing data about specific illegal behaviors.
3. Develop your analytical skills to produce strategic and tactical criminal intelligence reports that are useful.
4. Ensure that every piece of information given to the unit is secure and intact.
5. Follow the law and ethics when gathering information.
6. Create procedures for assessing how well the unit protects the privacy of all people whose information it has and how well it achieves its law enforcement objectives.
7. Create and preserve communication with law enforcement organizations at all levels to promote a productive sharing of intelligence regarding criminal cases (UNODC, 2011: 52).

By making its diagnoses and countermeasures for crime more relevant, criminal intelligence is committed to playing a crucial role in the functioning of the police system. After then, the investigation is put to use for intelligence purposes. Through case studies, the study helps to understand phenomena and criminal gangs, and intelligence gathers more information, processes it more rigorously, and offers a wider range of ways to capture them globally (Barlatier, 2020: 5). Jérôme Barlatier emphasizes that CRIMINT is thus a component of true risk management, in which the goal is to lessen uncertainty in a situation where knowledge is incomplete rather than to discover the truth. We are transitioning from the investigation's event-centered logic to a suspect-centered logic. The minority of the population that has chosen delinquency as their way of life is the focus of the police's attention. This strategy is required to dismantle the traditional compartmentalization that results from the division of judicial and administrative authority between security and justice-related acts. It promotes the development of a middle ground between these two poles (Barlatier, 2020: 5-6). It is expected that this continuum would create opportunities to go beyond the conventional division.

The creation of operational or strategic intelligence products that support diverse law enforcement objectives is the responsibility of criminal intelligence analysts. Strategic intelligence seeks to support appropriate modifications and improvements to laws, policies, and programs related to law enforcement, thereby fulfilling these agencies' long-term objectives on a national or international scale. Law enforcement officials can respond to current criminal activity locally by using operational intelligence to act upon the conclusions obtained throughout the intelligence analysis cycle. Tactical intelligence, which is the end result of tactical analysis, is another term for operational intelligence products generated by operational analysis (Groenewald, 2023: 19). At INTERPOL criminal intelligence analysts "are uniquely placed to recognize and detect patterns and criminal trends from a global perspective, and have the resources to assist with specific international crime cases" (Carter, 2009: 368). It is said that the notions of crime analysis and criminal intelligence are a part of a continuum of thinking and reasoning. Criminal intelligence analysts, on the intelligence side of the continuum, focus on examining substantial amounts of criminal behavior that have a detrimental impact on society. The idea is to establish links between such illegal acts in order to curtail or prevent them. Criminal intelligence analysts work with major crimes on the investigative end of the continuum. They piece together the events leading up to, including and following a homicide or a drug trafficking scenario (Groenewald, 2023: 43). Analysts of criminal intelligence may be tasked with tracking down criminals' movements and fixed locations. Locations where criminals congregate or sleep are referred to as stationary locations. Maps, and occasionally the combination of maps and timelines, can be used to ascertain the movements and lodging locations of offenders. The justification for the involvement of criminal intelligence analysts in this kind of work is that, if they comprehend the manner in which criminals navigate a certain region or

remain stationary, they will be more equipped to ascertain the appropriate course of action for further analysis. Their confidence in their anchor points grows as a result of this exercise. When participants can demonstrate how the map affected their comprehension of the offenders' movements or stationary points, this exercise can also be used as evidence of due diligence (reality/policy loop) (Groenewald, 2023: 193). Another responsibility for criminal intelligence analysts may be to ascertain whether there is a relationship between the offenders. Finding out who is phoning whom is one approach to achieve this. The relationship between artifacts and people can also be ascertained using a relationship diagram. An offender's contact with various items, such as a common phone number or license plate from an automobile, might be referred to as an artifact. Criminal Intelligence Analysts justify their involvement in this kind of work by arguing that by knowing who (or what) the criminals interact with (laddering, broadening), they will be better able to determine who to look into further (anchors, narrowing). Their comprehension of the criminals' social network grows as a result of this action (Groenewald, 2023: 199). These CRIMINT activities are very functional to proceed in analysis and to find solutions.

Covert information gathering methods are not the same as criminal intelligence. There is a widespread misperception that obtaining wiretap records, carrying out surveillance, and cataloging phone call logs constitute criminal intelligence. Regrettably, a prevalent belief among numerous law enforcement professionals is that any data acquired through clandestine means is classified as criminal intelligence. To describe this material as covert information would be more accurate. When covert information is examined and evaluated in light of all available knowledge about the topic under investigation, it becomes into criminal intelligence (Ratcliffe, 2007: 9). It is possible that some of the other sources – those that aren't secret – can be mixed with covert data to create intelligence. Surveillance photography and telephone wiretaps are examples of investigative equipment that are typically only instruments used to compile evidence against an offender. Thus, the work in this field is case support for investigations rather than intelligence. Information is considered criminal intelligence if it helps decision makers create a more comprehensive picture of criminality that they can then use to guide enforcement, prevention, or additional intelligence efforts (Ratcliffe, 2007: 9).

If we need to emphasize once again Criminal Intelligence (CRIMINT) is “the creation of an intelligence knowledge product that supports decision making in the areas of law enforcement, crime reduction, and crime prevention” (Ratcliffe, 2007: 8). Analysis is the core element of CRIMINT, without proper analysis and its presentation we cannot talk about intelligence.

Open, closed, and classified sources of information are the three primary categories of information in intelligence. Publicly available information is known as open source intelligence, or OSINT. “Gray literature” is one prominent category of open source content. Research, technical and economic studies, “white papers”, conference materials, theses and dissertations, discussion papers, newsletters on the topic, etc. can all be included. Evaluation is a major challenge when working with this kind of source because material that is in the public domain is frequently sensationalized, biased, or erroneous. Information gathered for a specific purpose and made unavailable to the wider public is referred to as a closed source (UNODC, 2010: 12). Structured databases are a common way to find information from closed sources. These databases will primarily contain personal information gathered as part of ongoing targeting activities, as well as more general criminal records, information on vehicle registration, weapons licenses, etc., in the context of criminal intelligence analysis. Information gathered through specially designated covert methods, such as the utilization of technological (image and signals intelligence) and human resources, is classified. Because classified information is typically quite accurate, using it can greatly improve the quality of an analytical result. However, due to dissemination constraints, using classified information can also dramatically reduce its actionability (UNODC, 2010: 12). The best way

is create an optimum balance to catch an actionable and practical solutions. Flexibility is the key for this, something open can be more functional and helpful then hidden elements.

CRIMINT analysis requires critical thinking always. Simply said, critical thinking is the act of considering what is being done, seen, or thought. People frequently carry out their work mindlessly, that is, applying the same strategy to many difficulties, and then wonder why the same issues keep coming up. Whether data has been around for a while or has only recently been gathered and retrieved, the intelligence process is always intellectual and can involve physical components. When the term “critical thinking” is used, it refers only to this method of thinking. When one applies critical thinking to an issue, other viewpoints are presented. There might be more explanations than these. If one interprets the data without considering all of the options, the analysis could be erroneous. A deadly error could result from analyzing a situation inaccurately (UNODC, 2010: 40). Critical thinking would help CRIMINT professionals to save them from this kind of mistakes.

Intelligence-Led Policing (ILP) gives more possibilities to CRIMINT activities. The concept of ILP describes a management framework for planned operational police work and criminal intelligence, where intelligence serves as the basis for establishing priorities and strategic and operational goals in the fight against crime and other security threats. It also entails allocating material and technical resources, rationally engaging the human resources that are on hand, and making the right decisions regarding operational police activities and actions (OSCE, 2017: 19). Because criminal investigation and criminal intelligence are fundamentally different from one another, crime analysis requirements are far simpler to satisfy than intelligence requirements. In essence, intelligence is driven by threats, whereas investigations are driven by crimes. Investigations are therefore reactive in nature, looking into crimes that have already happened and a known, quantified universe of facts that the inquiry has found. On the other hand, intelligence is proactive in that it takes action as soon as a threat is detected. In essence, intelligence is significantly more probabilistic and pre-crime, factors that provide problems for operations as well as civil right (Carter, 2009: 155). Law enforcement agencies in accordance with other governmental institutions need to find solutions for possible civil right problems.

Streets are crucial and important for ILP activities. The core question is “What types of information do street officers need from the intelligence function?” (Carter&Carter, 2009: 18). Intelligence analysis needs addressing four questions:

1. Who are posing threats? (people, ideologies, criminal threats against society).
2. Who are doing what with whom together? (descriptions, characteristics, connections).
3. What is the modus operandi that the threat has? (how they are working, in which way they attack).
4. What are needed to prevent the crime? (intelligence requirements, specific information) (Carter&Carter, 2009: 18).

CRIMINT process includes the steps of tasking and planning, collection and evaluation, collation and processing, analysis, reporting and dissemination of intelligence products, feedback and follow (OSCE, 2017: 30-41). All of these steps are directly or indirectly functional and helpful to officers on streets. Intelligence-led policing (ILP) is “a modern and proactive law enforcement model, and a realistic alternative to traditionally reactive forms of policing”. Intelligence-led policing “has already been adopted in a number of countries in recent years with promising results, combines intelligence gathering, evaluation and analysis with informed decision-making procedures and mechanisms, thus providing more efficient and effective management of national law enforcement” (OSCE, 2017: 4).

In criminal intelligence (CRIMINT) analysis, analysts gather intelligence in accordance with a predetermined intelligence procedure by adhering to management's instructions and tasking or investigators' demands. The primary component of the process is the analysis, although it also

involves information gathering, processing, and collation. In order to support criminal investigations and other law enforcement operations, as well as to prioritize and allocate technical and human resources, the analysis process produces strategic and operational criminal intelligence products. These products serve as the foundation for the development of strategic and operational plans (OSCE, 2017: 45).

There are many possible techniques in CRIMINT analysis, one of them is “network analysis”. This kind of analysis, especially in organized crime, gives some clues to the analysts (Sparrow, 1991). Three points are focused in this analysis:

1. Centrality (central, vital, key and pivotal actors).
2. Equivalence (analyzing uniqueness via equivalence models).
3. Weak ties (measuring strength and weakness in connections) (Sparrow, 1991: 263-272).

Basic techniques, their variations and interpretations by different agencies or different countries have been used. What are the main or basic techniques in CRIMINT? From one point of view the basic techniques may include link analysis, event charting (showing sequence of events; in complex cases it should be done early), flow analysis (flow of money, items, commodities, Etc.), and telephone analysis (UNODC, 2011b; 35, 49, 53, 59). These analyses need to be conducted by the CRIMINT analyst in a composition.

Agencies use the intelligence cycle when compiling criminal intelligence. The steps of this cycle: 1. Planning / direction 2. Collecting information 3. Processing / collation 4. Analysis 5. Dissemination 6. Evaluation and feedback (ACP, 2021: 15). But, what agencies? It depends of country, state and the time in history. In criminal intelligence several agencies need to share information; however many cultural issues may affect their interactions which are related to problems of ego, filtering, competition, mutuality, distrust, need-to-know and culture of secrecy (Australian Government, 2018: 5). Law enforcement agencies are performing CRIMINT activities usually. Although it is not very common to see an agency with a title particularly including the term of “criminal intelligence”, there are some examples. NCIS (National Criminal Intelligence Service, UK) was an interesting example.

Smage 3. NCIS Logo

To provide leadership and competence in criminal intelligence, the United Kingdom founded the National Criminal Intelligence Service (NCIS) in April 1992 and was “established as an independent organization on 1 April 1998 by the Police Act 1997 (the Act). Prior to that date it operated as part of the Home Office. The NCIS Service Authority was also created with effect from 1 April 1998, and it is the Service Authority that is the legal entity, as opposed to NCIS itself. This is the same as for a Police Force with regard to its Police Authority” (NCIS, 2005: 4). The organization strove to disrupt or apprehend significant offenders in the UK and targeted the highest levels of crime. NCIS, which was established in Europe to address the growth of criminal intelligence on a national level, employed about 500 people then from the Home Office, Customs and Excise, and

police. Through information processing and dissemination, direction and advice, and analysis of significant criminal activities, it sought to support law enforcement and other agencies both domestically and internationally (Global Security, 2024). NCIS consisted of the Headquarters (HQ), United Kingdom (UK), and International divisions in addition to a resources section. A policy and research unit, an intelligence coordination unit, an operational support unit, and a strategic and specialized intelligence branch were all part of the HQ Division. The latter's duties ranged from football hooliganism to organized crime. The UK Division, which was headquartered in London, was in charge of five regional offices: Wakefield, Birmingham, Bristol, Manchester, and London. It also had a Scottish/Irish Liaison Unit (Global Security, 2024). In addition to overseeing a network of DLOs (Drugs Liaison Officers) throughout Europe, the international division was connected to a global DLO network run by Customs and Excise. This division also housed the UK Bureau of Interpol, gave NCIS direct access to all 176 of Interpol's member nations. The information that NCIS processed was utilized to support police forces abroad and was essential in the fight against serious crime in the United Kingdom. The service collected intelligence on criminals from organized crime groups to money launderers (Global Security, 2024). NCIS merged into Serious Organised Crime Agency (Soca) in 2006 (Wright & Fickling, 2006). Therefore it had its position in the history.

Image 4. NCIS Plaque (DM, 2024)

According to the Annual Report 2004/05 NCIS delivers three main kinds of outputs for supporting the inter-agency strategies and collaborative projects. Operational intelligence on major offenders and their organizations; a variety of coordination services that support the multi agency law enforcement operations against serious and organized crime and the development of criminal intelligence; intelligence assessments that guarantee the extent of criminal threats and the nature of criminal business methods are properly understood and that law enforcement and policy makers learn the lessons of experience. Results NCIS does not conduct prosecutions, make arrests, or seize illegal materials (NCIS, 2005: 4). Along with partner agencies, NCIS works to: identify the proceeds of criminal activity and provide information that leads to the seizure of related criminal assets; reduce the risk that criminal activity will harm the UK and increase the risk that the criminal will do so; improve the chances that law enforcement will intervene; and remove opportunities for criminal activity. The Home Secretary and the NCIS Service Authority define annual goals and targets for NCIS, which are then published in a service plan. These results are intended to be ensured by the targets and objectives. The principles of NCIS by fostering and preserving an atmosphere that values employees, upholds professional standards, acknowledges accomplishments, and makes optimal

use of available resources, NCIS strives for the highest standards (NCIS, 2005: 4). Annual reports were like assessments of success levels towards these goals.

The Annual Report 2005-2006 says that as in the previous years the 2005/06 Service Plan outlined the ongoing Quality Program and highlighted the five key development areas of NCIS:

- consistently high performance,
- productively partner relationships,
- first class information / joined up systems,
- quality training / staff development,
- an estate fit for purpose ((NCIS, 2006: 14).

The work and activities conducted by NCIS, similar functions by similar agencies in the West, East and everywhere in the World were utilized by governments in their struggles against serious crimes which come most frequently with severe human rights violations by criminals. Organized crime or other types of serious criminal activities usually victimize the weakest and most vulnerable in societies. Of course sometimes the privileged classes and social groups can be victims of crime too. However, underprivileged, vulnerable populations are in lack of protection in streets and their social lives. Who will protect them? How will they survive in risky and problematic neighbourhoods? What are the ways to foresee and prevent crimes targeting them? This is exactly the point where the need for CRIMINT activities and institutions is arising. However, besides criminal intelligence agencies some other questions are arising too: in the age of growing sensitivity of human rights, data protection and freedom how can we be sure that our freedom and rights are not compromised in modern societies? What are the ways to protect human rights while securing societies in general? In which forms accountability can be maintained in CRIMINT related issues? The problem is to manage a perfect balance and harmony between security and human rights, protection and freedom.

Intelligence activities, in its all variations, should be conducted in model functional for all society, not only for intelligence agencies. Considering this societal approach, “an appropriate framework or a model is needed to manage the intelligence and to make maximum use of it, and to ensure that data and intelligence are gathered, processed and used in strict compliance with national laws and international human rights standards” (OSCE, 2017: 21). If there are contradictions with national laws or human rights concepts then there is a problem. Problems have to be solved in a democratic approach, in accordance with the values of society and humanitarian priorities. Human rights compliance has great importance “for both the short and long-term effectiveness of policing, including ILP. Law enforcement actions that fail to respect and protect human rights are counter-productive in the long term because they undermine public trust in the police and are also ineffective” (OSCE, 2017: 26). Every country needs to find proper ways to increase its human rights standards related to policing, security and intelligence. This is the best way both to improve the human conditions, level of human security and also effectiveness of existing security and intelligence services.

Law enforcement agencies’ possible mistakes may cause human rights issues. The plaintiffs must demonstrate both the law enforcement agency’s negligence and the existence of a pattern of misconduct linked to it in order for their civil rights lawsuit to be successful. This is usually accomplished by presenting proof that the law enforcement organization did not take reasonable steps to protect people's civil rights. In order to do this, the plaintiffs would usually try to show that the law enforcement organization intentionally displayed disregard for the defense of people’s civil rights and privacy (Carter, 2009: 156). This purposeful apathy in intelligence-related circumstances may result from factors like these:

- Lack of training: The organization does not give all law enforcement officers intelligence training in accordance with the guidelines set forth in the Global Advisory Committee's Minimum Criminal Intelligence Training Standards.
- Inability to direct: The organization lacks explicit policies and processes for gathering, retaining, reviewing, and disseminating criminal intelligence information.
- Failure to supervise: The organization either fails to enforce intelligence policy or fails to keep a sufficient eye on staff members' activities connected to intelligence.
- Lack of a privacy policy: In relation to intelligence and records management operations, the agency does not clearly define its policy to safeguard citizens' civil rights, privacy, and freedoms.
- Failure of maintaining standards: The agency does not follow the guidelines of the Commission on Accreditation for Law Enforcement Agencies' Intelligence Standards or the National Criminal Intelligence Sharing Plan, which are recognized professional standards of good conduct (Carter, 2009: 156-157).

Addressing possible diverse issues, three fundamental areas appear where civil rights problems are of concern: "Ensure that the collection and retention of information in a criminal intelligence records system are done in a proper manner, both legally and ethically. Ensure that individual privacy rights are protected for all information that has been collected and retained. Ensure the integrity of data quality and data security" (Carter, 2009: 159). Especially integrity of data has great importance in the age of internet and cyber world.

In order to not create any extra problems securely storing, accurately documenting and control of information / intelligence is of utmost importance. All intelligence and information files need to be maintained in accordance with the applicable law. Law enforcement or intelligence agencies should have the following elements: 1. Confidentiality, 2. Classification, 3. Access control, 4. Release, 5. Ownership (released material will remain property of the first agency), 6. Records management (IACP, 2021: 4). Observing the requirements of these elements is not only going to be functional and helpful to CRIMINT activities, it will be also perfectly instrumental to prevent many of the possible civil rights problems. When things are done properly the likelihood of human rights violations would be very low accordingly.

Conclusions

Criminal Intelligence (CRIMINT) through interactions with other fields related to security studies, intelligence studies and other disciplines of social sciences and humanities, has provided wide theoretical and possibilities to both scholars and practitioners. It is not easy to foresee the future of CRIMINT totally. However it would not be difficult to guess possible more involvement of technology and computer generated practices in analytical contexts. We need to understand something: computers, programs, any kind of existing and potential technology of future cannot bring magical solutions to neither CRIMINT nor any other discipline studying human societies. We should not be afraid of being accused as conservative, anthropocentric, Etc. just due to emphasizing the role of humanity and social actors on this academic and scientific ground. If we can talk (actually we must talk) about human security, human rights, peace and prosperity of people globally, we need to understand that this can be a work of only and only human beings. This is normal, this is just the right way. If lives of whales, frogs, bats or any other animal in nature should not be intervened by people unnaturally, in the same way human ecology, security and intelligence should be conducted by human beings normally, not by some technological apparatuses. We do not need to hesitate to say that there are still some things normal and abnormal as it will be forever. What is the message here? We just simply try to remind that let us not mistaken to overuse and be disoriented by technology. At the end of the day tools are tools to use, no need to fetishize them. We are pretty sure that practitioners understand us, we hope and believe that by intuition they agree with us too.

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